

Configurable PWM Generation with Hardware Debouncing for LED Brightness Control on FPGA: Verilog Implementation on the Tang Nano 1K Platform

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Abstract—This article presents the design, implementation, and analysis of a pulse-width modulation (PWM) generator with synchronous hardware debouncing and interactive duty cycle control, implemented in Verilog HDL on the Tang Nano 1K development board, equipped with the Gowin GW1NZ-LV1 FPGA, using the Gowin FPGA Designer Education environment (Gowin Semiconductor, 2023). The developed module, named `pwm_button`, generates a PWM signal at approximately 105 kHz derived from the board’s 27 MHz external clock, with duty cycle adjustable across 25 discrete levels of approximately 3.9% each, by means of a physical button with active-low logic and 20 ms time-window debouncing implemented entirely in synchronous logic. The asynchronous reset, equally active-low, restores the system to its initial state with the LED off. The results obtained on real hardware confirm a visually perceptible, gradual, and controlled variation of the onboard LED brightness, with robust operation under successive actuations and minimal utilization of the device’s logic resources. The work demonstrates the viability of low-cost FPGA platforms for the development and prototyping of embedded control systems with human-machine interfaces, with direct applicability in robotics, industrial automation, and reconfigurable hardware educational systems.

Index Terms—PWM, FPGA, Verilog HDL, debouncing, Tang Nano 1K, Gowin, embedded systems, brightness control, reconfigurable hardware.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pulse-width modulation is one of the most fundamental and widely employed techniques in power electronics, control systems, and embedded electronics. Its ability to control the effective amount of energy transferred to a load by varying the time a signal remains at a high level while keeping the frequency constant makes it suitable for applications ranging from DC motor speed control to switched converter regulation and LED-based lighting brightness control (Mohan et al., 2003). In robotic and automation systems, PWM is ubiquitous: linear actuators, servomotors, power controllers, and visual signaling interfaces frequently rely on this technique for precise and energy-efficient operation (Siciliano et al., 2009).

The implementation of PWM generators in dedicated hardware, particularly on FPGAs (Field-Programmable Gate Ar-

rays), offers advantages over microcontroller-based implementations: greater temporal determinism, absence of software latency, parallelism capacity inherent to the architecture, and dynamic reconfigurability without any physical hardware modification (Trimberger, 2015). According to Brown e Vranesic (2014), FPGAs allow control functions to be implemented directly in combinational and sequential logic, with timing predictable at the clock cycle level—a characteristic essential in real-time control systems, where temporal predictability is a design requirement rather than merely a desirable property (Buttazzo, 2011).

In this context, the present work aims to present, document, and analyze the implementation of a complete Verilog module for PWM generation with synchronous hardware debouncing and interactive duty cycle control on the Tang Nano 1K platform, discussing design aspects, implementation decisions, logic synthesis, and results observed on real hardware. The work is justified by the relevance of the topic to the robotics and automation community, by the growing adoption of low-cost FPGAs in educational and rapid prototyping environments, and by its contribution to the technical documentation of the Gowin platform in a formal academic context.

II. METHODOLOGY

The `pwm_button` module was described in Verilog HDL in accordance with the IEEE 1364-2005 standard (IEEE, 2006) and synthesized in Gowin FPGA Designer Education V1.9.11.03 for the GW1NZ-LV1QN48C6/I5 device in QFN48 packaging. Programming was carried out via the USB-C interface, using the BL702 programmer integrated into the board, with bitstream generation in the `.fs` format by the environment itself. The physical constraints file (`.cst`) defined the LVCMOS18 standard, with a bank voltage of 1.8 V for all signals, internal pull-up resistance enabled for buttons and reset, and a drive current of 8 mA for the LED.

The module was organized into three `always` blocks synchronized to the rising clock edge and two combinational

wire signals for logic inversion. Since the Tang Nano 1K buttons are active-low, connecting the pin to GND when pressed, the signals were inverted by `reset_in = ~reset` and `btn_in = ~btn`, establishing active-high internal logic and maintaining consistency with the positive logic convention.

Debouncing was implemented by a synchronous temporal filter. A 20-bit counter (`debounce_cnt`) increments while `btn_in` diverges from the stabilized state recorded in `btn_stable`. Upon reaching `DEBOUNCE_MAX - 1 = 539,999` cycles, corresponding to 19.999 ms at 27 MHz, the stabilized state is updated to the current value of `btn_in`, and the `btn_edge` signal is activated for exactly one clock cycle if the transition is from low to high. If the signal returns to its previous state before the time limit, the counter is reset to zero, guaranteeing immunity to instabilities shorter than 20 ms, as described by Ganssle (2004) and Dobkin e Williams (2011).

Brightness control uses an 8-bit duty cycle register. At each `btn_edge` pulse, the `duty_cycle` value is incremented by `STEP = 10`, corresponding to approximately 3.9% of duty cycle. When `duty_cycle + STEP` exceeds `MAX = 255`, the value returns to zero. The resulting sequence traverses the values 0, 10, 20, ..., 250 and returns to 0, yielding 25 distinct brightness levels.

The PWM signal is generated by a free-running 8-bit counter (`pwm_counter`), which naturally overflows every 256 clock cycles, resulting in a period of approximately 9.48 μ s and a frequency of approximately 105 kHz. The `led` output remains high when `pwm_counter < duty_cycle`, implementing the digital comparator responsible for pulse-width modulation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hardware verification confirmed the correct and robust operation of all functional blocks of the `pwm_button` module. The 20 ms time-window debouncing proved fully effective: each physical button press resulted in exactly one duty cycle increment, with no spurious increments, regardless of the speed or duration of actuation. This result quantitatively validates the choice of `DEBOUNCE_MAX = 540,000` cycles as sufficient for the tactile button used on the Tang Nano 1K, confirming the adequacy of the synchronous time-window filter technique for this class of components, as documented by Ganssle (2004). The determinism and precise response time control obtained are directly relevant to robotic applications, where embedded user interfaces must reliably respond to manual commands on control panels, operational mode selectors, and sensor calibration interfaces (Siciliano et al., 2009). Figure 1 presents the Tang Nano 1K, which comes with a button and LED for project evaluation.

The duty cycle progression followed the designed sequence, with the LED starting from the off state (`duty cycle = 0`) after reset and incrementing brightness at each button press in visually distinguishable steps. The luminosity variation was perceptible and gradual throughout the entire range, with increments at lower brightness levels producing more pronounced perceptual variation than equivalent increments

Fig. 1. Tang Nano 1K board (Sipeed, 2022).

at higher levels—behavior consistent with the Weber-Fechner Law and the logarithmic response of the human visual system to luminance described by Wandell (1995). This effect, while not compromising the module’s functionality for the proposed application, indicates that designs with perceptual linearity requirements should implement gamma correction curves in a lookup table (LUT-based gamma correction) within the FPGA itself, a technique described by Chu (2008) and feasible within the resources available on the GW1NZ-LV1.

The PWM frequency of approximately 105 kHz eliminated any perceptible LED flicker at all duty cycle levels, confirming the adequacy of the 8-bit counter for this application. For DC motor drive applications in robotic systems, where PWM frequencies in the range of 1 kHz to 20 kHz are preferred to minimize switching losses and acoustic noise (Mohan et al., 2003), the same module could be adapted by increasing the PWM counter width: an 11-bit counter would yield $27,000,000/2048 \approx 13.2$ kHz, and a 14-bit counter would yield $27,000,000/16384 \approx 1.65$ kHz, both within the appropriate range for small DC motors without any modification to the debouncing or duty cycle control logic. This parametric reconfiguration flexibility is one of the main advantages of FPGA implementation over fixed analog hardware solutions (Trimberger, 2015).

The active-low reset operated correctly, returning the duty cycle to zero and turning off the LED. The combinational wire inversion `reset_in = ~reset` was absorbed by the synthesizer without introducing observable additional logic in the synthesis report, with the inverters incorporated into adjacent LUTs at no additional area cost. As discussed in the theoretical background, the use of inverted combinational signals as asynchronous reset sensors is functional for prototyping and educational purposes, but designs with higher reliability requirements should implement explicit reset synchronization via a two-stage register, as recommended by Cummings (2002), to eliminate the theoretical risk of metastability in the FPGA flip-flops during the reset signal transition.

The Gowin FPGA Designer Education synthesis report indicated utilization of 38 flip-flops and fewer than 61 LUTs, representing approximately 5% of the 1,152 LUTs available on the GW1NZ-LV1. This result confirms that entry-level FPGAs are fully sufficient for PWM control modules with debouncing of this complexity, with ample margin for the integration of additional modules for serial communication, encoder reading,

multiple PWM channel control, or sensor signal processing in a more complete embedded system. The complete edit-synthesize-implement-program cycle was completed in a relatively short time, evidencing the efficiency of the Gowin development flow for rapid design iterations, a characteristic especially valuable in educational and robotics and automation prototyping contexts (Brown e Vranesic, 2014).

The source code of this work is available for download at <https://github.com/vitor-souza-ime/fpgapwm>.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrated the functional, robust, and efficient implementation of a PWM generator with synchronous hardware debouncing and interactive duty cycle control in Verilog HDL on the Tang Nano 1K platform, with real hardware verification in the Gowin FPGA Designer Education environment. The `pwm_button` module exhibited controlled and gradual LED brightness variation across 25 distinct levels, proven immunity to mechanical bounces of duration shorter than 20 ms, correct response to the active-low reset, and utilization of less than 5% of the GW1NZ-LV1 logic resources. The 105 kHz PWM frequency eliminated any perceptible flicker, and the duty cycle progression behaved as predicted by the theoretical analysis, with the perceptual non-linearity explained by the logarithmic response of the human visual system.

The work demonstrates that low-cost FPGA platforms such as the Tang Nano 1K are fully adequate for the development and prototyping of embedded control systems with human-machine interfaces, contributing to the democratization of access to reconfigurable hardware in educational and applied research environments in robotics and automation. As future work, it is proposed to extend the module to multiple independent PWM channels with configurable resolution, to implement lookup-table-based gamma correction for perceptual response linearization, to add UART serial communication for remote duty cycle control, and to implement explicit reset synchronization via a two-stage register for higher-criticality applications. Integration with DC motor H-bridge controllers and incremental encoder reading would constitute a complete servo drive system for low-cost educational robotics entirely implemented on an entry-level FPGA.

REFERENCES

- BROWN, S.; VRANESIC, Z. *Fundamentals of Digital Logic with Verilog Design*. 3rd ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2014.
- BUTTAZZO, G. C. *Hard Real-Time Computing Systems: Predictable Scheduling Algorithms and Applications*. 3rd ed. New York: Springer, 2011. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-0676-1>. Accessed: 14 Feb. 2026.
- CHU, P. P. *FPGA Prototyping by Verilog Examples: Xilinx Spartan-3 Version*. Hoboken: Wiley-IEEE Press, 2008. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470231630>. Accessed: 14 Feb. 2026.
- CUMMINGS, C. E. Simulation and synthesis techniques for asynchronous FIFO design. In: SNUG 2002 (Synopsys Users Group Conference, San Jose, CA, 2002) *User Papers*. 2002.
- DOBKIN, B.; WILLIAMS, J. (ed.). *Analog Circuit Design: A Tutorial Guide to Applications and Solutions*. Oxford: Newnes/Elsevier, 2011.
- GANSSLE, J. G. A guide to debouncing. *Guide to Debouncing*, Ganssle Group, Baltimore, MD, p. 1–22, 2004.
- GOWIN SEMICONDUCTOR. *GW1NZ Series FPGA Datasheet*. Version 1.5. Shenzhen: Gowin Semiconductor Corp., 2023. Available at: <https://www.gowinsemi.com/en/product/detail/2/>. Accessed: 13 Feb. 2026.
- IEEE. *IEEE Standard for Verilog Hardware Description Language: IEEE Std 1364-2005*. New York: IEEE, 2006. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.2006.99495>. Accessed: 14 Feb. 2026.
- MOHAN, N.; UNDELAND, T. M.; ROBBINS, W. P. *Power Electronics: Converters, Applications, and Design*. 3rd ed. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons, 2003.
- SICILIANO, B. et al. *Robotics: Modelling, Planning and Control*. London: Springer, 2009. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-84628-642-1>. Accessed: 14 Feb. 2026.
- SIPEED. *Tang Nano 1K: Hardware Documentation and Schematics*. Sipeed Technology Co., 2022. Available at: <https://wiki.sipeed.com/hardware/en/tang/Tang-Nano-1K/Nano-1k.html>. Accessed: 10 Feb. 2026.
- TRIMBERGER, S. M. Three ages of FPGAs: a retrospective on the first thirty years of FPGA technology. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, New York, v. 103, n. 3, p. 318–331, 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2015.2392104>. Accessed: 13 Feb. 2026.
- WANDELL, B. A. *Foundations of Vision*. Sunderland: Sinauer Associates, 1995.